

Exploring the value of Learning Analytics to enhance student learning and to enable more effective module management in large-class teaching environments.

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Abstract

The increasing use of digital Learning Management Systems provides educators, students and management in higher education with very significant amounts of data. However the effective use of this data, in the form of Learning Analytics, is still very limited in many institutions. In particular, the potential to use LA to support module delivery in large-class environments has not been significantly researched. This study examines the LA available on the Canvas LMS for a class of over 300 students, delivered fully online, to test the effectiveness, accuracy and usability of this data. There is a very strong correlation identified between the student engagement reflected in the Canvas analytics data and individual student performance, in the form of their final grade. However the analytics are more limited in terms of supporting self-regulated learning and identifying more nuanced student behaviour online. This study provides recommendations on how the LA data provided might be improved to enhance effectiveness for large-class teaching environments. This research also reveals other interesting patterns of learner behaviour that could assist educators with large classes, such as attention spans online and consistency of engagement throughout a module. The findings support the provision of lecture recordings online, as a revision tool, to enhance learning outcomes and engagement.

Keywords: *Learning Management Systems (LMS); Canvas; Learning Analytics (LA); Large-Class Teaching*

1. Introduction

It is widely recognised that the digital platforms now available to educators, commonly known as Learning Management Systems (LMS), can enhance the learning experience in a large-class setting (Murphy & Winkler, 2023). In many cases these systems can also reduce the administrative burden on educators in large-classes by facilitating more self-directed learning (Murphy, 2024). However, less consideration has been given to another benefit of LMS in large-class teaching environments, namely the provision of detailed data on student learning behaviour data, or Learning Analytics (LA). This research explores how the analytics from online learning platforms, in this case Canvas, could be used more effectively in the delivery of large-class modules. This is important where a one-to-one educational relationship with each learner is not viable. This research had two distinct aims:

- first, to determine to what extent the LA provided by Canvas are effective in terms of gauging student engagement, when compared to student performance (measured by final grade) and,
- secondly, to consider if the LA ‘dashboard’ (LAD) provided to both the educator and the student could be improved to further enhance module management, student performance and the learning experience.

Little research has been undertaken on this topic to date. The data from this research also provided other insights of to understanding online student behaviour in large classes where in-person management of each student’s individual learning is not feasible

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

The author delivers two large class-modules every year, approximately 330 students and 200 students respectively. For the purpose of this research, it was decided to select the largest module, in Business Ethics, for three reasons: a) it would yield more student data, b) it presents a more challenging module delivery context (with more student management) where this research could be of more benefit and c) the module was delivered completely online for two consecutive years (due to restrictions on in-person teaching related to the Covid epidemic of 2020 – 2022). This latter factor allowed for a complete measure of student engagement as all elements of the module were delivered online for this period, including (pre-recorded) lectures, via the Panopto platform embedded into Canvas. While this historic data was used as it offered the most complete LA set possible, the findings pertain to any measurement of online activity in a large-class setting, even where only some elements might be delivered online. As the module was delivered completely online for

two iterations, over two academic years, this also allowed for comparisons across both periods.

3. Literature Review

As Clancy et al. (2021) observe, there was a noticeable ‘digital pivot’ in education due to the Covid-era restrictions beginning in early 2020. This resulted in many academics embracing technologies that, while previously available, were not being widely used, and certainly not to their fullest potential. They also note the substantial benefits these technologies bring to the delivery of experiential learning in large-class teaching. The use of LA was of interest to researchers well before the Covid era. LA is defined as “*the measurement, collection, analysis, and reporting of data about learners and their contexts, for purposes of understanding and optimizing learning and the environments in which it occurs*” (Long & Siemens, 2011, p. 32, citing the definition given at the first international conference on LA, in Alberta, 2011). LA can be used for student management (such as gauging learning, identifying requirements for timely staff intervention, enhancing student retention) but also for self-regulated learning. LA has more potential to support higher education (Alfy et al. 2018), and while Sonderlund et al. (2018) do recognise educational institutions increasingly applying LA, they find there is little evidence of its effectiveness. Central to the current digital transformation of higher education, as part of the move towards the knowledge economy, is the ability of institutions to capture data on student engagement and outcomes attainment (Alenizi, 2021). However, LA is still considered to be an ‘emerging area’, with most developments ‘in the pilot phase’ and ‘without reaching institutional adoption’ (Marquez et al., 2023). These researchers also claim that the current analytic tools being made available on most LMS tend to originate from the data available rather than the needs of students and teachers. Furthermore they state that most LA tools are evaluated on their usability rather than their usefulness. Arthars and Liu (2020) see little stimulus for the application of LA from top management; they believe a ‘bottom-up’ approach is more likely to succeed, when individual educators realise this potential for their own teaching. By monitoring module analytics throughout the semester, educators can identify behaviour and performance indicators pro-actively and help students to perform better in the module (Dietz-Uhler & Hurn, 2013). One of the very few researchers to specifically examine LA in a large-class context state that identifying stronger and weaker attainment groups is harder in large classes, but LA may be of benefit (Aghav and Aghav, 2014). Matcha et al. (2019) find that most LA dashboards are not grounded in learning theory and fail to provide effective learning tactics. Viberg et al. (2020) see little evidence to date of LA supporting improvements in self-regulated learning, but they view this more as a lack of using LA mechanisms to support student learning rather than just measure it.

Like others, above, they state more research is required to better exploit the potential offered by LA to support learning.

Given the potential for LA to be of even greater benefit to supporting self-regulated student learning and student management in large-class environments, this research is timely.

4. Empirical Methodology/Data

A substantial data set of a large-class module delivered fully online, on two separate occasions, over two academic years, was selected. The first aim was to explore what LA were available on the Canvas LMS platform, and to investigate if this could be correlated to student performance (measured in terms of final grade) in a large-class setting. Little research has been undertaken to date seeking to measure online student engagement in relation to student performance, using large-scale data sets.

4.1. Data Sets

Data from the analytics tools on Canvas and Panopto (the online lecture recording function used via Canvas) for two academic years were downloaded for every student with each student's identity being anonymised. As the Panopto facility was set to only allow student viewing via Canvas, the full record of viewing time / engagement was recorded. These recordings could not be downloaded to view offline. Final grades for every student, for all exams (a mid-term and an end-of-term exam, also conducted via Canvas) were also downloaded separately.

4.2 Analysis

A data analyst was hired, with the support of SATLE (Strategic Alignment of Teaching and Learning Enhancement) funding from the Irish Higher Education Authority, given the very large amount of data to be processed and analysed over a number of weeks. The first action was to identify what data was already available from the Canvas and Panopto LA functions. These proved to be very limited in terms of providing in-depth and specific metrics for each student in an accessible format. A lengthy process of downloading data for each of the over 330 students, over two iterations of the module, to calculate their level of engagement with each element of the module (e.g. readings, lecture viewing minutes, lecture notes) for each week. This data was very time-consuming to collect and collate. It also had to be anonymised to meet ethical approval requirements. The first stage of analysis was to see how the individual levels of student engagement compared to final student performance, in terms of the module grade achieved. Different types of engagement (e.g. lecture minutes viewed) were correlated with student performance and combined engagement (e.g. lecture

viewing and reading) was also used. The second stage of the analysis was to examine other patterns of student learning behaviour recorded and to consider how this might be used more effectively for future applications of LA. In both stages the focus was on how very large levels of student engagement data, based on large classes, could be managed more effectively.

4.3. Findings

The initial analysis examined student performance in relation to student engagement as recorded on Canvas and Panopto. There was a very strong correlation noted between engagement on two key elements (number of minutes spent viewing online lectures and readings, the two main components of module content) and individual student performance, in terms of the final grade. Indeed the researcher and analyst found they could frequently predict a student's grade to within a few marks, based on their engagement profile in the LA used. Predictability of learning outcomes is also considered a benefit of LA (Smith et al., 2012). These researchers discovered that the frequency with which students logged into their LMS and engaged with the online material predicted their overall performance.

This graphic shows how individual grades compared to module engagement on the two key elements of (online) lecture minutes viewed and engagement with readings.

Figure 1. Student exam performance in relation to module engagement LA

The analysis also identified a significant number of students who had very low engagement throughout the module (and whose final performance reflected this). In the most extreme

cases, some students had barely engaged at all (and failed the module). This would not be apparent in a large-class with hundreds of students and it emphasised the value of having such analytics to notify the lecturer of poor engagement levels while an intervention may still be possible. At the other end of the performance spectrum, the data showed that the top-scoring students had engaged beyond the 100% limit used for LA metrics (in other words, they may have viewed the same lecture material a number of times, but the LA would only note them as having reviewed it in full, i.e. 100%). Therefore their viewing minutes for each lecture (video) had to be manually calculated and combined to give a total score, beyond 100%. This will be discussed later as it also relates to the value of having lecture recordings online as a revision tool for more motivated students.

The second stage of the data analysis investigated the overall module activity, as recorded by the LA, to investigate how this might inform effective use of LA in large-class settings. This analysis showed some very interesting patterns of behaviour, in terms of the extent and timing of student engagement, apart from a very clear divergence in overall engagement between the high and low-scoring students. In line with expectations (and previous research ref) student engagement dipped as the semester progressed and peaked again before any exam (mid-term and end-of-semester exams). However the data was very noticeable in terms of the sharp drop in engagement at certain points of the semester, and this suggests a need to have more frequent moments of compulsory engagement / assessment.

Figure 2. Engagement rate throughout the semester

The increase in engagement mid-way through the semester is likely explained by a mid-term in-class exam for 50% of the module grade. The much higher engagement at the start of the first year of analysis, 2020, might be explained by the fact that this was during a complete ‘lock-down’ so there were few alternative activities, or distractions, available to students. There may also have been a ‘novelty factor’ as this was the first time these students would have undertaken an online only module. The second year of the module was delivered online, in 2021, when most other classes, with less than 300 students, were being delivered back in-person, on-campus, and most lock-down restrictions had been lifted.

The data also demonstrated how student engagement varied according to the length of video material.

Figure 3. Video completion rates according to the length of individual videos

This graphic above shows how the LA metrics, using class averages, can give misleading data regarding actual engagement, when the data from those who did not engage at all is removed. It shows a much higher engagement level than the metrics might indicate, when only measured by those who did actually engage. It shows that on the longer videos the completion rates were generally not quite as high, particularly on Video 1., the longest. This could also be a case that, as the first video of the module, some students had not fully

engaged in the program yet. However, these findings would tend to support other research that suggests that video length can impact engagement levels (Walsh et al., 2021).

There was also consistency in terms of a student's individual engagement across the different elements, so if they did not view many lectures, they were also less likely to have clicked on the readings. This demonstrates that even where LA are only used on some elements of a module delivery (where there might be in-person lectures), they are still very useful for the purposes discussed above. The findings also highlighted other limitations of the aggregated LA provided by Canvas.

5. Analysis of/Reflection on/Implications for Practice

This research is exploratory and seeks to build on other research, also in its infancy, in terms of how LA might be more effectively harnessed to not only support student learning but also to support module management for large-classes. It provides in-depth data that has been lacking to date, demonstrating the effectiveness of LA to reflect student learning behaviour in a large-class teaching environment. It also demonstrates that LA can be very effective in predicting student performance outcomes. This can assist educators to monitor student engagement early in the module and intervene appropriately. However this research reinforces previous concerns, above, that the LA on LMS are not generally 'user-friendly' for either educators or students, but that they do offer potential to all stakeholders, including management. The findings demonstrate the possibility of monitoring individual student engagement and presenting data pro-actively (e.g. as a warning in case a student has not engaged adequately for a number of weeks). This could be given automatically to the student directly, in the first instance, to motivate them to engage, and, if no visible change is noticed in the LA, a warning about this student could be sent to the lecturer. For those teaching large classes, this could be of great benefit.

A potentially greater benefit of LA in enhancing student learning in large classes relates to self-regulated learning. Providing students with real-time data of student activity on a module could motivate students to increase their engagement in the module; select peer data rather than module averages is likely to be more motivational (Fleur et al., 2023). Such real-time engagement data could, perhaps, be coupled with predicted performance outcomes based on previous module performance, such as that collected for this research.

Additionally there was an unexpected finding with regard to the very high viewing rates (more than 100%) of lecture material (pre-recorded videos) by higher-performing students. This would support the case for uploading recordings of lectures (including for in-person module delivery) to facilitate the learning of more motivated students. In many institutions the provision of lecture recordings is only required for students requiring extra supports. However, making lecture recordings available to all students on a module, particularly in a

large-class context, also needs to be considered in the light of concerns relating to a negative impact on in-person lecture attendance.

The total time spent on a platform, while it might be considered a good proxy of total student engagement, does not allow for the fact that students may be downloading material and engaging off-line. One way to control this is to only allow recorded material, via Panopto, to be viewed online. This also reduces the possibility of recorded material, particularly lectures, being shared inappropriately (if staff have concerns about misuse of their intellectual property etc.). The LA on engagement in readings are also limited in that it does not record reading activity undertaken off-line

Any initiative to use student behaviour analytics should be presented as a means to enhance student engagement and success, and not some form of punitive monitoring. Otherwise students may attempt to 'game the system' by leaving the LMS open for long periods, downloading but not reading material etc.

A large amount of research remains to be undertaken to identify the best ways to utilise and present the enormous data now available to educators, managers and students from LMS. This research shows the potential of LA to support a number of areas relating to learning and student management, but it also highlights the difficulties with current systems and approaches, particularly for large-class teaching environments.

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